

Effects of micrometeoroids on GAIA attitude

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SAG-LL-031

ABSTRACT

The effects of micrometeoroids on the along-scan attitude of GAIA are estimated and compared with the limiting attitude estimation accuracy (in the absence of other noise sources). It is concluded that micrometeoroids have negligible effect on the overall astrometric accuracy. Several impacts per hour will however be detectable in the a posteriori attitude determination.

ASSUMPTIONS

Only the motion about the spin (z) axis is considered. The change in rotational velocity d_{ω} (rad/s) is calculated from:

$$d_{\omega} = m * r * v / I$$

where

m = particle mass in kg (according to mass spectrum below)
 r = typical impact distance from z axis = 3 m
 v = rms tangential velocity of particle = 12000 m/s
 I = spacecraft moment of inertia about z axis = 7000 kg m².
[Note: no number for the moment of inertia was found in the study report. It was therefore estimated from available masses and dimensions: S/C excluding solar panels/shield (2000 kg cylinder of 2.1 m radius) = 4400 kg m²; solar panels/shield (R = 4.25 m, 5.3 kg/m²) = 2700 kg m².]

$v = 12000$ m/s in one coordinate corresponds to a mean (rms) total velocity of 20 km/s, which is quoted as a typical impact velocity.

With numbers inserted, a convenient rule of thumb is that $m = 1E-12$ kg corresponds to $d_{\omega} = 1$ uas/s (micro-arcsec per second).

The flux of particles (in impacts/m²/s/hemisphere) with masses greater than m (kg) is given by

$$F(m) = \begin{cases} 2.8E-11 * m^{(-0.5)} & \text{for } m < 2.8E-11 \text{ kg} \\ 2.6E-18 * m^{(-7/6)} & \text{for } m > 2.8E-11 \text{ kg} \end{cases}$$

according to Yamakoshi (Extraterrestrial dust, ASSL 181, 1994).

The rate of impacts on the solar panel/shield (R = 4.25 m), considering both hemispheres, is roughly $100 * F(m)$ per second.

RESULTS

The smallest particles that need to be considered are about

$m = 1E-13$ kg, giving a typical d_{ω} of 0.1 uas/s. The rate of these is $100 * F(1E-13) = 0.01$ per second, i.e. mean time between impacts is $T = 100$ s. This means that the vast majority of the "frames" (0.86 s exposures) are completely undisturbed by micrometeoroid impacts.

Whether an impact is detectable depends on how accurately the spin rate (ω) can be determined before and after the impact. This in turn depends on the lengths of the "quiet" intervals before and after the impact. If we neglect the FEEP noise (which may not be possible!) we find that in a time interval of length T (s), the spin rate can in principle be determined with accuracy

$$\sigma_{\omega} = 4 * \sqrt{P_0} * T^{(-1.5)}$$

where $P_0 = 1000 \text{ uas}^2 \text{ Hz}^{(-1)}$ is the low-frequency attitude estimation floor derived in SAG-LL-020, or

$$\sigma_{\omega} = 126 * T^{(-1.5)}$$

For instance, particles of $m = 1E-13$ kg, with a mean interval of impacts equal to $T = 100$ s, gives $\sigma_{\omega} = 0.13$ uas/s, whereas the effect of the impact is $d_{\omega} = 0.1$ uas/s. These events are therefore not detectable at 1-sigma level.

However, taking $m = 1E-12$ kg gives $d_{\omega} = 1$ uas/s, $T = 1/(100 * F(m)) = 360$ s and $\sigma_{\omega} = 0.02$ uas/s, so these impacts should be detectable at the 5-sigma level (provided other noise sources can be neglected).

To upset the real-time guiding system will require a rate error of the order of one sample (37 mas) per frame (0.86 s), or $d_{\omega} > 40000$ uas/s. According to the previous formulae this will happen for $m > 4E-8$ kg, or with frequency $100 * F(m) = 1E-7$ per second, i.e. at intervals of a few months.

In a 5 year interval, the largest expected impact will have $m = 5E-7$ kg, producing a rate discontinuity of 0.5 arcsec/s. With a typical thruster torque of $2E-3$ Nm, this could in principle be corrected in just 10 s.

CONCLUSIONS

Significant (i.e. potentially detectable or disturbing) impacts will happen at intervals of minutes, rather than seconds, and the a posteriori attitude determination will be able to cope with these without compromising the final accuracy. However, a large number of events will be detectable and the attitude software has to take this into account (rate discontinuities to be inserted as required). Impacts large enough to (temporarily) upset the real-time operation will be rare.
